

COMPARISON OF KISS-BOND AND DIS-BOND DEFECTS IN CFRP LAMINATES BY COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT TESTING

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ABSTRACT

Kiss-bonds are structural defects, common to adhesive bonding applications, that feature a localised loss of structural continuity between two surfaces exhibiting intimate contact. Such defects are a problematic precursor to damage growth and structural failure but are notoriously difficult to detect. In order to better study the detection and influence of kiss-bonds in composite structures, a novel pre-curing approach has been developed for the manufacture of artificial kiss-bonds – which avoids the use of inclusions or contaminants that are common to previous studies. Small square defects have been manufactured in Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) samples, and evaluated using Non-Destructive Inspection (NDI) techniques and microscopy. The resulting defects were all found to be detectable using modified NDI practices but classified, based on industrial criteria, as either kiss-bonds (no detectable voids by conventional NDI) or dis-bonds (containing detectable voids). Samples with kiss-bond defects, dis-bond defects or no defects were then damaged with 10.5 J impact energy and re-assessed by ultrasonic C-scan. Impacted samples with pre-existing kiss-bonds resulted in damage areas around 30% greater than those of pristine samples, on average, and 15% greater than those of samples containing dis-bonds. Compression After Impact (CAI) testing has also been performed with specialised anti-buckling fixtures to assess any effect on mechanical performance. Kiss-bond and dis-bond samples were found to perform similarly, both showing only a slight reduction in compressive strength compared with the control samples. Ultimately, small kiss-bond and dis-bond defects of a detectable size (100 mm²) appear to have a negligible effect on the compressive performance of a thin laminate after a coincident low energy impact event.

1 INTRODUCTION

As the adoption of advanced composite materials continues to grow in aircraft, automotive and other structural applications, there is increasing research interest in maintenance-related activities such as inspection and repair. Conventionally, structural repairs in the aerospace industry have relied upon mechanically-fastened patching methods, stemming from established and reliable practices on metallic airframes. However, the drilling of composite materials is problematic as it can result in local delamination and moisture ingress. Such patching methods also add significant weight to the original structure. Hence, adhesively-bonded scarf repairs are a desirable alternative as they can provide more efficient load transfer through the repaired structure with a minimal effect on the weight and aerodynamic profile of the structure.

The primary challenge for airworthy adhesive repairs, is the need for reliable assessment of the bonding quality and greater confidence in the bonding strength. Defective bonds with zero strength, often termed “kiss-bonds”, remain a major concern for certification bodies, as they are difficult to detect by conventional Non-Destructive Inspection (NDI) techniques. Such defects are internal, invisible from the exterior surfaces and can evade ultrasonic detection as they are many orders of magnitude thinner than a n ultrasonic wavelength [1]. Although their cause is not always clear, kiss-bonds are often associated with poor adhesive chemistry, incorrect cure processing, contamination, residual stress or moisture ingress [2].

1.1 Definition of kiss-bonds

Considerable research effort has attempted to define, replicate and interrogate kiss-bond defects for a range of adhesive bonding applications, not only composite repair. This has resulted in some inconsistency in the definition of kiss-bonds and their classification. Early definitions, such as those by Brotherhood et al. [1], suggested that there are at least two different classifications of kiss-bonds: those that are formed between contacting “dry” adherends, and those that include a thin “wet” layer of liquid between two surfaces. Alternatively, Marty et al. [2] state that kiss-bonds must achieve a lap shear strength below 20% of the nominal adhesive performance, exhibit purely adhesive failure, and be undetectable by conventional ultrasonic C-scans. Another common classification considers kiss-bonds as zero-volume dis-bonds, where there is intimate contact between one adherend and the adhesive layer but no physical or chemical bonding between them [3].

In this paper, kiss-bonds are defined as dry, zero-volume defects that provide no shear strength. These are distinguished from dis-bond defects, which have an easily detected gap or void between surfaces, similar to delamination. Defects that provide some, albeit greatly reduced, bond strength are instead considered “weak bonds”. This classification, where kiss-bonds are an intermediate condition between dis-bonds and weak bonds, has also been used in other recent literature [4].

1.2 Replication of kiss-bonds

In order to better study the detection and structural influence of kiss-bonds and weak bonds, researchers must first attempt to scientifically replicate these defects. Three main methods have been adopted to produce artificial kiss-bond defects: compressed plates, inclusions and contaminants. In the first case, parallel metal or glass plates, either with or without an adhesive layer on the surface of one plate, are employed to represent a kiss-bond defect between adherends under pressure [5–7]. This approach simulates a defect across the full bonding area, usually for the purpose of assessing different NDI capabilities against a bonded control case.

For composites specifically, other researchers have attempted to recreate kiss-bonds by introducing solid materials such as fluoropolymer films into a subset area of the adhesive bonding region [8, 9]. However, these inclusions are not representative of true zero volume defects as they change physical properties (such as acoustic impedance) across a finite thickness within the structure and are detectable using standard ultrasonic [10] and other NDI methods [8].

Alternatively, another popular method for producing artificial kiss-bonds is to introduce contaminants such as release agents, oils or greases onto one of the bonding surfaces [3, 8, 10–12]. This is generally considered the simplest approach and may be a better representation of the true cause of kiss-bond defects, but this “wet” contamination process is not easily controlled or reproduced. Several of these studies report Frekote 700 NC release agent to be the most effective source of contamination for the production of artificial kiss-bonds [3, 11, 12]. However, another study has produced contradictory evidence, where Frekote was seen to migrate into the adhesive and was therefore not considered appropriate for the preparation of kiss-bonds [8] (in agreement with advice from Marty et al. [2]).

Aside from these three main methods for defect production, other research has considered employing adhesives with dissimilar shear strength in different subsections of a bonding region [13], electrically releasing epoxies [2], or liquid resin filling [14].

Due to the uncertainty associated with the existing methods for producing artificial kiss-bonds, this research has been performed using a new pre-curing method, specific to composite laminates.

2 MANUFACTURE OF ARTIFICIAL KISS-BONDS

2.1 Materials

An aerospace-grade Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) prepreg material, with a 5-harness satin weave, has been used in this work. Pristine and defect panels were all prepared from a symmetric layup of 8 plies, for a nominal sample thickness of 2.8 mm, following manufacturer guidance.

2.2 Method

A novel method of producing artificial kiss-bonds by pre-curing small areas of two adjacent plies has been developed at the University of Limerick [15]. Small regions of the prepreg are carefully cured under direct pressure using electric heating elements of the desired defect size. The local curing process in these areas has been validated by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), to ensure full curing of the matrix material. A portion of the surrounding area was also tested to ensure that no curing occurred by any heat radiating out from the proposed defect area. Peel ply and vacuum bagging material between the heating elements and the prepreg help ensure a smooth surface finish. Using this approach, any degree of partial curing could also be investigated for the potential to produce repeatable weak bonds of varying strength. When included within a normal composite layup and curing process, the two adjacent pre-cured regions will remain unbonded and create the desired zero-strength defect. For all samples in this study, defects were generated between the middle two plies of the layup.

3 DEFECT INSPECTION

3.1 Ultrasonic classification

Once manufactured, the panels with artificial defects were scanned independently at three different institutions to classify the resulting defects as either kiss-bonds (easily missed by standard practice) and dis-bonds (easy to detect). Defects that had been unanimously identified as either kiss-bonds or dis-bonds were classified as such, while samples with conflicting classifications from different institutions were excluded from final testing. Although these kiss-bond defects were not obvious when following standard industrial practice, a more thorough interrogation could detect the artificial kiss-bonds reliably at sizes as small as 6 x 6 mm [15]. It is expected that poor ply alignment or entrapped air are the cause for the poorer quality dis-bond defects.

3.2 Microscopy

Representative samples of the two different defect classifications from NDI (kiss-bond and dis-bond defects), were evaluated by microscopy. Specimens were carefully cut to prevent any further damage as a result of vibration or shear loading, then mounted in resin for subsequent grinding and polishing. Images were taken with both an optical microscope and a Hitachi FlexSEM-1000 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). In both specimens, the middle pre-cured plies in each defect sample were found to be flat, with a 50-100 μm thick resin-rich region between them, as seen in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

In the kiss-bond specimen, a long, continuous and fine crack-like feature was observed, at the interface between the pre-cured plies (see Figure 1). The thickness of this kiss-bond interface was notably smaller than 5 μm , and extended across the full width of the pre-cured region, until reaching a small lip, seen in the SEM - A inset of Figure 1. This lip was likely the result of a partially-cured region of resin spew from the pre-curing process.

The dis-bond specimen also exhibited some fine crack features; however, a number of large and inter-connected voids (>50 μm thick) were evident between the pre-cured ply regions (see Figure 2). These void areas also included a considerable volume of "loose resin" that did not appear to be

attached to either of the adjacent pre-cured plies (but was concluded not to be grinding debris from the polishing process).

Figure 1: Cross-section of an artificial kiss-bond, including SEM images from the end (SEM - A) and middle (SEM - B) of the defect area [15].

Figure 2: Cross-section of a dis-bond defect, with SEM image of deep voids (SEM - C) [15].

4 IMPACT TESTING

4.1 Method

Impact testing was performed using a drop weight impactor, with rebound prevention, for batches of 5 or more pristine, kiss-bond and dis-bond samples. A 10.5 J impact energy was selected as this was the lowest energy to consistently achieve fibre breakout at the back face of panels, with barely-visible damage on the impacted surface and a minimal dent depth. The aim was to balance the introduction of internal damage via impact with the existing internal defects to try to observe any differences between kiss-bond, dis-bond and pristine samples. Greater impact energy would be more likely to mask or overpower any effect from the pre-existing defects.

4.2 Non-Destructive Inspection (NDI) results

After impact, samples were again inspected using a phased-array ultrasonic scanner to determine the size of the induced impact damage. Representative examples from pristine, kiss-bond and dis-bond samples are shown in Figure 3. Generally, the kiss-bond samples showed the greatest damage areas, followed by the dis-bond samples. The pristine samples exhibited less damage as a result of the 10.5 J impact. The average results are shown in Figure 4 along with the standard deviation among each sample batch.

Figure 3: Representative examples of C-Scans taken after impact in 100 x 150 mm samples.

Figure 4: Mean damage areas resulting from 10.5 J impact in samples with or without pre-existing defects.

Using statistical analysis, assuming that the true mean values of two different sample groups are equal, a p value was calculated as the probability of seeing the observed difference, or greater, between mean results. In this way, the difference between the observed results of two sample groups can be considered as statistically significant (p value <0.05) or not (p value >0.05). The increased damage size in the kiss-bonds relative to the pristine samples is considered statistically significant (p value 0.016); however, the difference between the dis-bond samples and pristine samples is not (p value 0.230). Kiss-bond samples also appear likely to have a greater damage area than the dis-bond samples (p value 0.051).

5 COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT (CAI) TESTING

5.1 Standard test rig

Initial CAI testing was conducted according to ASTM D7137-12 [16] and monitored with a combination of Digital Image Correlation (DIC) and strain gauges to assess the degree of buckling in the composite samples. As expected, since these samples were around 1 mm thinner than the recommended minimum standard thickness of 4 mm, considerable buckling behavior was observed and the samples failed in the unsupported region near the top fixture. Hence, an alternative anti-buckling fixture had to be adopted.

5.2 Anti-buckling test rig

Custom-built anti-buckling fixtures were used to conduct more appropriate CAI testing. These consisted of two similar rigid fixtures that fully constrained the front and back surfaces of the samples, aside from a 40 mm diameter circular window on each side that allowed for unconstrained compression. Using this approach though, it was no longer possible to employ strain gauges or DIC.

A minimum of 5 impacted samples were tested for each batch: pristine, kiss-bond and dis-bond. Additionally, a single “compression only” sample without impact damage from each configuration was also tested. The pristine sample without impact damage failed in a less supported area far from the gauge region, while both defect samples without impact damage failed due to end crushing. All three “compression only” samples failed at similar loads, with invalid failure modes. Hence, these tests may not be representative of the true compressive strength, but still serve as a reasonable reference for the CAI tests.

The full results from “compression only” and CAI testing can be seen in Figure 5 for samples with and without defects. Compared with the “compression only” results, the impacted samples showed >40% reduction in compressive strength, all with valid failure modes through the middle of the impact site due to the targeted constraints of the anti-buckling fixture.

Figure 5: Compressive strength results for pristine, kiss-bond and dis-bond samples, with and without impact damage. Samples without impact damage failed either far from the gauge area *, or by end crushing **.

To better visualise the differences between the CAI samples, Figure 6 displays the mean results and standard deviation. Again, by considering the null hypothesis, the significance of these results has been assessed. The difference between kiss-bond and dis-bond CAI results shows no statistical significance (p value 0.342). It is also unlikely that the 5% reduction of kiss-bond samples relative to pristine CAI samples is statistically significant (p value 0.123). However, the 8% reduction of dis-bond samples compared against the pristine samples is considered significant (p value 0.019).

Figure 6: CAI results for pristine, kiss-bond and dis-bond samples with 10.5 J impact.

The relationship between impact area and compressive strength has also been investigated for the pristine, kiss-bond and dis-bond samples in Figure 7. Although there does not appear to be any significant trend to relate compressive strength with damage area within the scattered results.

Figure 7: Relationship between ultimate strength and impact damage area for pristine, kiss-bond and dis-bond samples.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Kiss-bonds have been artificially manufactured in prepreg laminates using a novel pre-curing approach that allows for reliable and controlled production. Samples containing these defects have been classified as either kiss-bonds or dis-bonds independently by three different institutions, based on the difficulty of detection, according to industrial NDI practice. With targeted NDI methods, all 10 x 10 mm defects were found to be detectable. The existence of kiss-bond defects appeared to produce damage areas 15% and 30% larger than dis-bond and pristine samples after a 10.5 J impact event. However, neither the size of these damage areas nor the type of defect (or indeed whether there was a defect) appeared to affect the Compression After Impact performance of the 8 ply CFRP laminates. These results are significant as the ability to detect kiss-bonds is an important step in enabling the aerospace industry to take a damage-tolerant design approach for future bonded repairs in aircraft. Demonstrating that kiss-bonds, at a detectable size, behave similarly to dis-bonds (and pristine laminates) after a low energy impact event, is an encouraging step in the path to certification. However, further work will still be required to investigate damage growth in fatigue.

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